

Edited by Dr. Heba Sophia Ibrahim
PHENET | Communication & Dissemination

Welcome to the 3rd PHENET Newsletter!

As PHENET is now in its fourth year, we are reaching an important stage in the project. What began as a collection of innovative ideas, technologies, and collaborative developments is progressively taking shape as a portfolio of services designed to benefit the wider research and innovation community.

This issue highlights a significant milestone: nine PHENET-related services are now available, spanning data management, image analysis, reference datasets, and landscape monitoring. These achievements illustrate our collective ambition not only to develop new methods and technologies, but also to ensure that they become sustainable and accessible resources within European Research Infrastructures.

The examples presented in this newsletter demonstrate the diversity of PHENET's impact. From AI-powered tools for wheat disease assessment to high-resolution soil health mapping across contrasting European landscapes, PHENET continues to show how phenotyping, envirotyping, data science, and artificial intelligence can be combined to address key challenges in sustainable agriculture and environmental stewardship.

Equally important is the growing engagement of our community. Our upcoming General Assembly and External Stakeholder Session at UCLouvain will provide an opportunity to showcase concrete outcomes, gather feedback from users and stakeholders, and discuss pathways towards long-term adoption.

As we approach the final phase of the project, our focus is increasingly on ensuring that PHENET's results outlive the project itself through robust services, strong partnerships, and integration within the future European research infrastructure landscape, notably through the progress of EMPHASIS towards ERIC status.

I would like to thank all partners, contributors, and stakeholders for their continued commitment and enthusiasm. Together, we are building foundations that will support the next generation of agroecological research and innovation.

Bertrand Muller, PHENET coordinator

In this newsletter...

COORDINATOR'S MESSAGE

A word from Bertrand Muller

WP1 SERVICES

Nine PHENET services now available
Datasets, tools & platforms live

INTERCROPAGENT

AI-driven intercropping literature
mining

BIOHACKATHON 2026

Dedicated seat for PHENET in
Göttingen

USE-CASE SPOTLIGHT

Plant health · Soil mapping

EMPHASIS NEWS

Research Infrastructure updates

STAKEHOLDER SESSION

10 September · UCLouvain

ECPN

ECPN General Assembly at the IPPS9

EVENTS

IPPS9 · AnaEE Conference 2026

News from PHENET

WP1 · TASK 1.2 · SERVICE DEVELOPMENT

Building the PHENET service portfolio

Nine PHENET-related services are now Available and published on the PHENET website, while additional services are either partly finalised or under active development. Ongoing work focuses on refining service maturity classification and strengthening the transferability of Use Case developments into sustainable RI services.

In parallel, discussions with research infrastructures have been initiated. Further engagement activities are planned during the General Assembly and through a webinar series beginning in September 2026, aiming to showcase PHENET services to the RI community, gather feedback, and support future service adoption.

Explore the full catalogue:

https://www.phenet.eu/en/services_from_phenet_categories

Contributed by Thi Ly Mai · ly.mai@anaee.eu

AI INNOVATION · LITERATURE MINING

IntercropAgent: using AI to accelerate intercropping literature mining

Manual extraction of data from scientific literature is a time-intensive process. To address this challenge, PHENET researchers have been collaborating with AI experts in Berlin to explore the potential of artificial intelligence for automated data extraction from the intercropping literature.

This collaboration was initiated at the BioHackathon organised by the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) in Walsrode, Germany, in December 2025.

Building on a manually curated dataset of intercropping experiments in Europe, the team is developing and training an AI model specifically for this extraction task. **The objective is to create an Intercropping Data Extraction Agent:** an intelligent tool that will allow users to upload scientific papers and automatically extract relevant agronomic data. In the final stage, the team plans to publish both the research paper and the agent itself, alongside guidance on its application and a discussion of its performance, possibilities, and limitations.

Service portfolio at a glance

DATASETS

Global wheat | Orchard phenotyping

DATA MANAGEMENT

Phenotyping Hybrid Information System (PHIS)

IMAGE ANALYSIS

DeepPhenoTree | ECCV 2026 CVPPA

LANDSCAPE

SoilMap: high-resolution mapping of forest soil

CONSULTING

Wheat biotic stress

MONITORING / EXPERIMENTAL PLATFORM SERVICE

Horizontal root monitoring (Rhizotron)

ANALYTICAL SERVICE

Stable isotope labelling for soil microbial carbon dynamics

The project is open for collaboration. Interest PHENET members are invited to join the team!

CONTACT

Madhur Paul

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Madhuri Paul presenting the intercropping data extraction use case at the BioHackathon Germany, December 2025 | Photo credit: Lea Kabjesz.

From Our Community to PHENET

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT · BIOINFORMATICS

PHENET at BioHackathon Germany 2026: a dedicated seat for the project

The 5th BioHackathon Germany will take place at the Hotel Freizeit-In in Göttingen from 7–11 December 2026. Organised by the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI), this event is a central forum for tackling key challenges in life science and bioinformatics, bringing together researchers and developers to advance open-source tools and data infrastructure through focused, collaborative work.

PHENET is pleased to announce that a dedicated seat has been sponsored for the project at this year's BioHackathon. This is a unique opportunity to advance PHENET-specific goals, including data interoperability, AI-driven analysis tools, and community-driven development, while collaborating with the broader bioinformatics community.

To ensure all interested consortium members have the chance to participate, the internal application deadline is **15 July 2026**. Further information:

<https://www.denbi.de/de-nbi-events/2051-5th-biohackathon-germany>

Contributed by Daniel Wibberg

5th BioHackathon Germany

DATE

7-11 December 2026

LOCATION

Hotel Freizeit-In
Göttingen, Germany

ORGANISER

de.NBI - German Network for
Bioinformatics Infrastructure

PHENET SEAT

One dedicated seat sponsored for the
consortium

APPLICATION DEADLINE

15 July 2026

CONTACT

Daniel Wibberg
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Use-Case Spotlight

New computer vision tools help to assess wheat ear diseases

PHENET's Use Case 1 on plant health is validating sensors and imaging methods for the assessment of wheat ear diseases, with two AI-powered applications now reaching proof-of-concept stage.

The first, **FUSASEYD**, addresses Fusarium Head Blight (FHB), a major fungal disease in winter wheat. Using RGB field images and a deep learning instance segmentation model (**YOLOv11**), the application detects and quantifies FHB symptoms on wheat ears, offering an automated alternative to time-consuming expert visual scoring. GEVES has developed both a PC interface and a smartphone application to visualise model predictions in the field. Validation in French registration trials is planned for the 2026 campaign. A companion article by V. Cadot *et al.* is currently under review in the Journal of Experimental Botany special issue on Plant Phenomics & Enviromics Across Scales.

The second, **COYL (Counting Orange and Yellow Larvae)**, tackles a practical challenge faced by breeders, and rapidly counting wheat blossom midge larvae, both *Sitodiplosis mosellana* and *Contarinia tritici*, to characterise variety susceptibility. Using smartphone RGB images and YOLOv-based object detection, the best-performing model achieved high accuracy and successfully distinguished between the two visually similar species. An online counting application has been developed, currently accessible to Walloon Agricultural Research Centre members.

The labelled COYL-1 dataset is publicly available at [10.5281/zenodo.19402333](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19402333) for community use. A companion article by Antoine Deryck *et al.* is under submission at Plant Phenomics Journal.

Contributed by Philippe Philippe Vermeulen

USE CASE 2 · SOIL HEALTH

Mapping soil health from Austria to Portugal: digital soil surveying with Subterra Green

A novel approach to in situ soil data acquisition and analysis, reaching to 90 cm depth, is being demonstrated through PHENET's Use Case 2. Using the **Subterra Green** proximal soil sensing platform from S4 Mobile Laboratories, researchers from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU) and the University of Porto are generating high-resolution digital soil maps with a focus on **soil organic carbon (SOC)**, a key indicator of soil health and carbon sequestration potential.

The system combines Vis-NIR spectral measurements with machine learning and digital soil mapping techniques to monitor spatio-temporal variability of soil physico-chemical properties. Field campaigns have been conducted at two contrasting sites:

- ▶ **Austria (AGES site):** examining the effects of tillage management, comparing conventional and pioneer treatments, on SOC distribution at depth.
- ▶ **Portugal (Idanha-a-Velha, Montado ecosystem):** landscape-scale SOC mapping, using remote sensing data from PHENET's WP3, to facilitate planning in soil sampling design. By integrating proximal and remote sensing with AI and machine learning

The project demonstrates the potential for large-scale implementation across European land-use systems, from agricultural and grazing to forested landscapes. Validated techniques support evidence-based land management, precision agriculture, and climate mitigation strategies. Initial results are being presented at EGU and PHENET webinars, with full publications in preparation.

Read more about **Subterra Green**:

[10.5281/zenodo.20829302](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20829302)

Contributed by Akos-Etele Csibi

Meet the Research Infrastructures in PHENET: News from EMPHASIS

EMPHASIS advancing towards an ERIC

EMPHASIS, the European Research Infrastructure for Plant Phenotyping, continues to advance rapidly. ERIC Step 1 was submitted to the European Commission on 30 October 2024 by the relevant Belgian national authority, with 10 countries included. Since then, EMPHASIS has focused on preparing its ERIC Step 2 submission and developing a strong application for ESFRI Landmark status. After joining the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016, the research infrastructure is now closer than ever to achieving this major recognition. The Landmark application was submitted on 15 December 2025, followed by the ESFRI Hearing in early May 2026.

ERIC Step 2 is planned for submission by June 2026, with the ambition of **establishing EMPHASIS as an ERIC** and launching its operational phase in early 2027. This timeline depends on the European Commission's evaluation and the publication of the ERIC decision in the Official Journal of the European Union.

In early 2026, Dr. Susie Robinson took up the role of Interim Director-General, guiding the Coordination Office through this decisive phase and has recently been confirmed as the inaugural Director-General once EMPHASIS ERIC is established.

Throughout 2026, EMPHASIS Scientific Leads have been actively shaping the ambitious and exciting programme that will unfold once EMPHASIS ERIC is established, setting the stage for a transformative operational phase. This included an action-packed 'Spring Gathering' in Portugal in late April.

EMPHASIS Spring Gathering with EMPHASIS Scientific Leads.

PHENET External Stakeholder Session

GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2026 · OPEN EVENT

See PHENET in action: technologies, tools, and services at the General Assembly Stakeholder Session

On **Thursday 10 September 2026, 14:00–17:00 CEST**, PHENET will open its doors to external stakeholders as part of the annual General Assembly. The event will be hosted at the **Earth & Life Institute, UCLouvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium**.

This dedicated External Stakeholder Session offers researchers, policymakers, breeders, agri-tech companies, and civil society organisations an opportunity to engage directly with the technologies, services, and tools developed across PHENET's use cases, many of them now moving from validated prototypes towards future European research infrastructure services.

Eight use case demonstrations will be on show, spanning plant health monitoring, soil phenotyping, multi-scale wheat phenotyping, orchard phenology, ecosystem analysis, intercropping data intelligence, landscape soil health mapping, and pollinator ecosystem indicators. Visitors will have the opportunity for one-on-one exchange with the technology developers themselves.

Attendance is free but spaces are limited. Registration is required.

Read More about the event in our flyer: [10.5281/zenodo.20747176](https://zenodo.org/record/20747176)

For questions, contact us at phenet@fz-juelich.de

WP6 · Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

Event Details

DATE & TIME

Thursday, 10 September 2026 14:00–17:00 CEST

VENUE

Earth & Life Institute UCLouvain Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

ADMISSION

Free · Registration required Spaces are limited

USE CASES ON SHOW

- ▶ [G3 smart glasses & wheat disease detection](#)
- ▶ [Digital soil surveying with Subterra Green](#)
- ▶ [Multi-scale wheat phenotyping](#)
- ▶ [Orchard phenology \(Phenomobile\)](#)
- ▶ [Ecotron soil phenology](#)
- ▶ [IntercropAgent \(AI literature mining\)](#)
- ▶ [SoilMap for landscape monitoring](#)
- ▶ [Bee colonies as ecosystem indicators](#)
- ▶ [IoT sensor networks for real-time field monitoring](#)

REGISTRATION

[Register here](#)

Upcoming Events

9th International Plant Phenotyping Symposium (IPPS9)

Accra, Ghana · The Palms by Eagles

Co-hosted by International Plant Phenotyping Network (IPPN) and the West Africa Centre for Crop Improvement (WACCI), IPPS9 is themed “Phenotyping for all: Closing the Gap in Global Agriculture.” Sessions cover field phenotyping under climate extremes, below-ground phenomics, next-generation precision breeding, and multiscale phenomics from molecules to ecosystems.

When: October 12-16, 2026

Abstract & travel grant deadline: 1 July 2026

Registration closes: 1 October 2026

More information: www.plant-phenotyping.org/ipps9

2nd AnaEE Science Conference

Menton, France · Palais de l'Europe

Themed “Ecosystem Science for a Resilient Future,” this conference brings together ecosystem scientists, policymakers, industry, and stakeholders. AGROSERV and M4C will be represented through a dedicated workshop. Topics span global change ecology, forest and agricultural resilience, aquatic-terrestrial interactions, and innovative data methods.

Accessible from Nice International Airport.

When: 29 September – 1 October 2026

More information: indico.anaee.eu/event/5/

ECPN General Assembly at the IPPS9

Accra, Ghana · The Palms by Eagles · Room TBA · Remote access available

The Early Career Professionals Network's General Assembly is the annual meeting of the Early Career Plant Phenotyping Network (ECPN), bringing together early-career researchers working in plant phenotyping, crop physiology, imaging, modelling, data science, and related fields.

Why is this relevant at IPPS9? The general assembly provides a dedicated space for ECPs to connect, exchange experiences, and discuss current challenges and opportunities in the plant phenotyping space to strengthen their involvement in the broader phenomics community and ensure that the perspectives of PhD students, postdocs, technicians, and industry professionals are represented at the international stage.

Who is your target audience? Our target audience is the early-career professionals attending IPPS9 as well as anyone interested in supporting, mentoring, training, and community-building activities in plant phenotyping.

What will be done? During the general assembly, we will introduce the mission and ongoing activities of ECPN since its launch, present future initiatives, and discuss opportunities for collaboration. Crucially, the new board elections will be held, and the new coordination team will be announced during this session! We invite participants to join the network and encourage them to become actively involved.

Who is organising this & what for? This event is organised by the ECPN board team to strengthen and inspire the ECP phenomics community. Whether you want to run for a board position, join a working group, or simply meet peers in your field, we warmly invite you to join us!

When: October 16, 2026 | 16:45-18:00

Contact: [Rhianna McAneny](#), [Carlos Robles](#)

Stay Connected & Updated

Our website
www.phenet.eu

Our LinkedIn Page
PHENET Project

Our Zenodo Community
zenodo.org/communities/phenet

Let's Innovate Together
phenetinnovation.slack.com

Thank you to all contributors and partners!
Stay tuned for our 4th issue (late 2026).

Have a question? Contact us:
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